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SOCIO-ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR ENHANCING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH AND INCENTIVE SYSTEMS IN THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR

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Abstract. This article analyzes the issues of increasing the efficiency of research and development work in the agricultural sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the introduction of innovative developments into production, and the motivation of scientists. The purpose of the study is to show the ways to achieve economic growth by strengthening the ‘science-education-production’ chain in the agricultural sector. Based on statistical data, the article examines the reforms implemented in the industry in recent years, in particular, the introduction of the cluster system and its integration with scientific research. The analysis shows a direct correlation between the increase in investment in research and development and crop yields and labor productivity. The article also highlights the institutional and economic conditions necessary to increase the innovative activity of researchers, taking into account international experience and local characteristics.

Keywords: agriculture, scientific research, efficiency, incentives, innovation, agro-industrial cluster, labor productivity, economic growth.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируются вопросы повышения эффективности научно-исследовательских работ в сельскохозяйственном секторе Республики Узбекистан, внедрения инновационных разработок в производство и стимулирования ученых. Цель исследования — показать пути достижения экономического роста путем укрепления цепочки «наука-образование-производство» в аграрной сфере. В статье на основе статистических данных рассматриваются реформы, реализованные в отрасли в последние годы, в частности, внедрение кластерной системы и ее интеграция с научными исследованиями. Анализ показывает наличие прямой корреляции между увеличением объема инвестиций в научные исследования и урожайностью, а также производительностью труда. Также в статье освещаются институциональные и экономические условия, необходимые для повышения инновационной активности исследователей, с учетом международного опыта и местных особенностей.

Ключевые слова: сельское хозяйство, научные исследования, эффективность, стимулирование, инновация, агропромышленный кластер, производительность труда, экономический рост.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern world, agriculture is not only a sector that ensures food security, but also a strategic field in which advanced technologies and scientific achievements are increasingly integrated. The agricultural sector plays a decisive role in the sustainable development of Uzbekistan’s economy. According to statistical data, the agrarian sector accounts for approximately 18–20 percent of the country’s gross domestic product (GDP) and provides employment for a significant share of the population.

However, challenges such as global climate change, water scarcity, and land degradation require comprehensive modernization of the sector and the wider introduction of science-based approaches. In this process, the role of scientific research is of particular importance, since only through innovation is it possible to save resources and increase productivity.

Current national development priorities emphasize the need to raise the integration of science and practice in agriculture to a new level. This task is aimed at comprehensively supporting the activities of agricultural scientists and improving the practical effectiveness of their scientific developments. At present, more than 350 agro-industrial

clusters operate in the republic, and their cooperation with research institutions is becoming one of the key factors of the sector's intensive development.

The promotion of scientific activity includes not only financial incentives, but also the creation of modern infrastructure for research, the attraction of international grants, and the protection of intellectual property rights. This article focuses specifically on the socio-humanitarian aspects of managing agricultural science, namely the development of human capital and motivation mechanisms.

To improve the effectiveness of scientific research in agriculture, it is first necessary to enhance the social status of scientists and introduce a system for assessing their work based on market principles. This would help reduce the gap between science and production and strengthen their practical integration.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The issues of promoting innovative processes and scientific research in agriculture have been studied by many foreign and domestic scholars. Representatives of classical economic theory, including Adam Smith and David Ricardo, emphasized the importance of technological innovation in increasing labor productivity in agriculture. Joseph Schumpeter, in turn, described innovation as the "internal engine" of economic development and paid particular attention to the relationship between entrepreneurship and scientific activity.

Among modern researchers, M. Porter developed the theory of enhancing competitiveness through the cluster approach, which today forms one of the conceptual foundations of Uzbekistan's agrarian policy [2, p. 12]. Among domestic scholars, A. Abduvakhidov and J. Kucharov, in their studies, substantiated the need to improve the mechanisms for training agricultural personnel and financing research institutions in the context of Uzbekistan [4; 7]. According to them, the low level of commercialization of scientific developments slows the introduction of innovations into the sector.

In addition, reports by international organizations, including the FAO and the World Bank, note that in developing countries, funding allocated to agricultural research should amount to at least 1 percent of GDP, whereas in Uzbekistan this indicator still remains relatively low. The literature review shows that technical modernization alone is not sufficient to increase scientific efficiency; the humanitarian factor, namely the motivation and creative freedom of researchers, is also of significant importance.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employed the methods of systematic analysis, comparative economic analysis, and statistical grouping. The activities of research institutes and agro-industrial clusters operating within the system of the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan were selected as the object of the study.

The database was formed using reports and official publications of the Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Agriculture, and international financial institutions for the period 2018–2024. In addition, national target indicators related to agricultural development and innovation were analyzed.

During the research process, a correlation analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between expenditures allocated to scientific research and the yield of major agricultural crops, particularly cotton and grain. This method made it possible to quantitatively assess the impact of scientific investment on real production.

Within the humanitarian dimension of the study, the results of surveys conducted among scientists and sectoral specialists were also taken into account. These results helped identify shortcomings in the existing incentive system.

The methodological basis of the study is the "Science–Policy–Practice" model in the agricultural sector. This approach makes it possible to evaluate scientific outcomes not only from a theoretical perspective, but also in terms of their social and economic effectiveness.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

As a result of reforms carried out in Uzbekistan's agriculture over the past five years, the sector has demonstrated stable growth dynamics. By the end of 2024, the volume of gross agricultural output increased by 4.4 percent compared to the previous year and reached 467 trillion soums. A significant part of this growth is attributable to clusters that have introduced innovative technologies.

However, the effectiveness of scientific research has not yet fully reached its potential. The analysis shows that the volume of public expenditures and international grants directed toward scientific research has been increasing, which is directly reflected in productivity indicators. For example, while the average cotton yield was 23 centners in 2017, by 2024 this figure had reached 34 centners. Table 1 presents the dynamics of research expenditures and crop productivity.

Table

Dynamics of Scientific Research and Crop Productivity in Uzbekistan's Agriculture in 2018–2024¹

1.

Year	Research expenditures (trillion soums)	Cotton yield (centners/ha)	Grain yield (centners/ha)
2018	0.8	24	45
2020	1.2	27	48
2022	1.9	31	52
2024	2.5	34	55

The figures presented in the table indicate that the funds allocated to scientific research have increased almost threefold over the past six years. This, in turn, contributed to an increase in grain yield from 45 to 55 centners per hectare. It should be noted that the implementation of scientific results in practice has accelerated through the cluster system. At present, 355 clusters are working directly with scientists on the basis of contractual agreements.

The results of the analysis show that the effectiveness of scientific research in agriculture depends not only on financial resources, but also on the quality of management. The introduction of the cluster system in Uzbekistan has contributed to reducing the existing gap between science and production. However, incentive mechanisms continue to show a relatively centralized character.

International experience, including that of Israel and the Netherlands, shows that the income of researchers should be linked to a certain percentage of the profit generated from their scientific developments. In the context of Uzbekistan, however, researchers' remuneration is largely based on fixed salary schemes, which may limit their interest in commercially oriented innovations [9, p. 33].

From the perspective of the humanities, psychological and social support for agricultural scientists is also important. Studies show that for young researchers, housing benefits and opportunities to participate in international conferences often serve as stronger motivational factors than monetary rewards.

On the other hand, improving the effectiveness of scientific research requires the broader application of the concept of "Digital Agriculture." This is not only a technical process, but also a social process that requires improving the digital literacy of personnel. Although the statistical analysis shows that productivity growth has mainly been driven by intensive factors, its sustainability in the future will largely depend on high-tech innovation. Therefore, improving the incentive system on the basis of performance-based evaluation remains an important priority.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Improving the effectiveness of scientific research and strengthening incentives for researchers in the agricultural sector are of strategic importance for ensuring the country's sustainable economic growth. Based on the results and analysis conducted in this study, the following conclusions were drawn.

First, along with increasing the amount of funding allocated to research activities, it is necessary to strengthen control over the targeted use of these funds and their orientation toward final practical outcomes. Second, in order to further deepen the integration of science, education, and production, small innovation centers and experimental laboratories should be established within agro-industrial clusters.

Third, to ensure fair assessment of the work of scientists and researchers, a transparent mechanism should be created for distributing income generated from authors' royalties and patents. Fourth, in order to attract young scientists to the sector and retain qualified scientific personnel, they should be provided with long-term preferential loans and social support packages, they should be provided with long-term preferential loans and social support packages.

Fifth, strengthening international cooperation, involving leading foreign experts in local projects, and encouraging Uzbek researchers to publish articles in reputable international journals will increase the global competitiveness of the sector.

Overall, only by investing in human capital and creating a free and innovation-oriented research environment can Uzbekistan's agricultural sector be transformed into a high-tech and profitable industry.

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¹ Source: Compiled by the author based on official statistical data and sectoral reports.

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